

Disease brief_Hepatitis E

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Hepatitis E is a viral disease in animals (such as domestic pigs, wild boar, deer, shellfish) and in humans. In humans, Hepatitis E virus (HEV) is the most common cause of acute viral hepatitis world-wide (1).</p> <p>Hepatitis E virus (HEV) is a Orthohepevirus A with different genotypes and belongs to the family of Hepeviridae. HEV is a single-stranded, nonenveloped, RNA virus and one of five known human hepatitis viruses: A, B, C, D, and E. Four genotypes of HEV are endemic in different regions in the world infecting humans only (HEV-1 and HEV-2) or both humans and animal species (HEV-3 and HEV-4). Other closely related strains with limited public health relevance have been detected in a range of animals including wild boars (HEV-5 and HEV-6), rabbits (HEV-3ra) and camels (HEV-7 and HEV-8) (2; 3).</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	Hepatitis E is a non-WOAH-listed disease. Hepatitis E is also not notifiable at the European level, neither in humans nor in animals. However, notification may be required in individual Member States.
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>In animals, Hepatitis E is reported more or less worldwide. Most commercial-scale pig farms producing slaughter pigs are likely to be infected (4). In European countries, more than 50% of the pig farms may be affected, with seroprevalence within farms of 80 % or higher (2).</p> <p>Human hepatitis E cases have been increasingly reported in Europe over the last 10 years. HEV-3 is described as the most common cause human hepatitis E virus infections (1). Only a few locally acquired infections with HEV-4 viruses have been reported from France, Italy and Germany (2).</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>The main reservoir hosts are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic Pigs (<i>Sus scrofa domesticus</i>) (HEV-3 and HEV-4) • Wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) (HEV-3 and HEV-4). <p>HEV-1 and HEV-2 have been found only in humans (5).</p>

5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	In addition to pigs and wild boar, HEV-3 and HEV-4 and/or anti-HEV antibodies have been identified in a wide range of animal species including deer, moose, rats, dogs, cats, mongooses, cows, sheep, goats, avian species, rabbits, bats, horses and shellfish (reviewed by EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2017), without causing any disease.
6	Vector-borne transmission	No.
7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	<p>HEV RNA can be detected in contaminated water and other materials in contact with HEV-contaminated pig manure. In relation to water, different types of samples need to be considered, including drinking water, irrigation water or wastewater.</p> <p>Contamination of the environment with HEV from human and animal faecal waste may furthermore lead to contamination of fruit and vegetables, and bivalve molluscs.</p>
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	<p>In developed countries, HEV is mainly transmitted to humans through consumption of contaminated, not-properly-cooked pork or game meat or other meat products, but also through shellfish or contaminated vegetables (HEV-3 and HEV-4), while in developing countries the faecal-oral route predominates (HEV-1) (1).</p> <p>Person to person transmission of the HEV-3 is very rare (5).</p> <p>Occupationally exposed groups with direct contact to infected animals or their organs, e.g., slaughterhouse and forestry workers, hunters, farmers and veterinarians show higher seropositivity than the general population (1).</p>
10	Disease indicators	
11	a) Clinical signs	<p>HEV leads to subclinical infection in animals.</p> <p>In pigs, low-grade transient hepatitis has been reported only after experimental infection of pigs (10).</p>

	Shedding/detectability of pathogen	<p>After a latent period of 1 – 2 weeks, pigs start shedding for 1 – 7 weeks (predominantly via faeces). Viraemia lasts for about 1 – 2 weeks (11).</p> <p>The level of viraemia and faecal shedding of HEV at slaughter varies according to several factors, including management system, the age at first exposure and slaughter age. The small intestines, lymph nodes, colon and liver are the primary sites for HEV RNA detection (12).</p> <p>On farms, the first shedder of HEV is usually detected in the nursery room. The peak in virus shedding in faeces is reached within 12 – 14 weeks. After moving the pigs to the fattening room, a steep increase is seen in the number of HEV shedders on farms (11).</p>
12	b) Seroconversion	<p>Seroconversion starts approximately 3 – 4 weeks after infection, with unknown duration (11).</p> <p>On infected farms, piglets show declining levels of maternal antibodies during the first 7 weeks. Antibody titres increase starting from week 8 and may reach their maximum in week 12 (IgM) and at slaughter age (IgG).</p>
13	c) Other disease indicators	No.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Due to the absence of clinical signs or other disease indicators in animals, no relevant indicators used for monitoring are described in literature.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>Identification of the agent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard method: PCR (conventional PRC, RT-PCR, PR-qPCR, LAMP). Assays for the simultaneous detection of genotypes 1–4 are available and have been used with human, animal, food or environmental samples. - Alternative method for serum or faeces: ELISA/EIA. EIA showed lower sensitivity compared with RT-qPCR (13). - HEV is difficult to culture. For HEV cell culture systems a high detection limit and varying reproducibility were described (14). - For food products, no standardised method for detection, quantification or typing of HEV is available so far (2).

		<p>Serological tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard screening test: ELISA (15). - Availability of commercial assays for detection of IgM and IgG against HEV-3 and HEV-4 in food-producing animals is limited. - Alternatives: commercial kits optimised for detection of human anti-HEV antibodies have been adapted to use for swine or other animal species. In-house indirect or blocking ELISAs using HEV-3- or HEV-4-related ORF2 proteins are also available. - Cave: test characteristics vary between the different available assays and may reveal discordant results (16).
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pathogen detection in pigs breeding stock 2. Pathogen detection in effluents from farms and abattoirs in high-risk sites in high-risk seasons <p>Rationale: These options focus on pathogen detection in domestic animals where the consequences of spread could be higher.</p> <p>Additional relevant components not included in this brief include pathogen detection in slaughter pigs and pathogen detection in hunted wildlife before human consumptions. These two components have a focus on food safety and are therefore considered out of scope for the EU4Health programme initiative "CP-g-22-04.01".</p> <p>HEV may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by HEV (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 34,5% species are "Near Threatened", 34,5% are "Vulnerable", 13,8% Endangered, and 17,2% Critically Endangered (CR) (17).</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
Non vector-borne diseases									
Hepatitis E	Pigs								Pathogen detection in pigs breeding stock
									Pathogen detection in slaughter pigs - Surveillance component not eligible for funding (focus on food safety)
	Wildlife (wild boar, deer)								Pathogen detection in hunted wildlife - Surveillance component not eligible for funding (focus on food safety)
	ENVIRONMENT								Pathogen detection in effluents from farms and abattoirs in high-risk sites in high-risk seasons
	Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope
17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>GENERAL REMARK: in all surveillance components described below samples could be used for detection of additional pathogens.</p> <p>1. Pathogen detection in breeding stock.</p> <p>ADVANTAGES: Pathogen spread to a lower level in the pig production pyramid could be reduced by testing pigs before mixing of different groups or movement to other farms. HEV can be detected earlier on farm in a pig's life compared to sampling at the abattoir. Sampling of faeces is non-invasive. The HEV-status of a farm or production unit can be determined or confirmed. On a national level, a baseline overview on HEV situation in the pig production sector and detected changes in prevalence and pathogen distribution can be gained. If positive samples are sequenced, a better understanding in genotypes and subtypes circulating within the country can be gained, including how animal genome sequences relate to human cases. Diagnostic test system is already established in MS. Samples could be used for detection of additional pathogens.</p> <p>DISADVANTAGES: Depending on the sampling process, costs of sampling on farm might be more expensive compared to sampling at the abattoir. Limited options for risk-reducing measures based on the test results if there are no HEV-negative farms in the area from which HEV-negative animals could be purchased.</p>							

		<p>2. Pathogen detection in effluents from high-risk sites in high-risk seasons.</p> <p>ADVANTAGES: Testing of water samples allows to also cover other priority pathogens.</p> <p>DISADVANTAGES: Diagnostic test system potentially not established in all MS.</p>
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	<p>Surveillance activities take place in most of the main pig producing countries. EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (2017) reviewed HEV surveillance activities in 15 countries. More recently, 9 countries carried out surveillance on pig farms within the One Health EJP Biopigee project (BIOPIGEE - One Health EJP). Boxman et al. (2022) identified 13 studies from 9 countries in which pigs were sampled at the abattoir for HEV (18).</p> <p>In humans, HEV testing is established in 26 countries and 19 countries sequence HEV (19).</p>
19	References	<p>1) ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), 2017. Facts about hepatitis E. Factsheet. Available online: https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/hepatitis-e/facts.</p> <p>2) EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards), Ricci A, Allende A, Bolton D, Chemaly M, Davies R, Fernandez Escamez PS, Herman L, Koutsoumanis K, Lindqvist R, Nørrung B, Robertson L, Ru G, Sanaa M, Simmons M, Skandamis P, Snary E, Speybroeck N, Ter Kuile B, Threlfall J, Wahlström H, Di Bartolo I, Johne R, Pavio N, Rutjes S, van der Poel W, Vasickova P, Hempen M, Messens W, Rizzi V, Latronico F and Girones R, 2017. Scientific Opinion on the public health risks associated with hepatitis E virus (HEV) as a food-borne pathogen. EFSA Journal 2017;15(7):4886, 89 pp. https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4886.</p> <p>3) Primadharsini, P. P., Nagashima, S., & Okamoto, H., 2019. Genetic variability and evolution of hepatitis E virus. <i>Viruses</i>, 11(5), 456.</p> <p>4) Salines M, Andraud M and Rose N, 2017. From the epidemiology of hepatitis E virus (HEV) within the swine reservoir to public health risk mitigation strategies: a comprehensive review. <i>Veterinary Research</i> 48(1), 31.</p>

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